

EBFMC25-OP-51 · Have Outpatient Visits and Hospital Admissions for COPD Remained Stable Over the Last 10 Years?

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is the leading non-communicable chronic respiratory disease world-wide (Boers et al., 2023). In 2019, the global prevalence of COPD was estimated at approximately 400 million cases (Adeloye et al., 2022). This study aimed to evaluate and compare the characteristics of COPD patients admitted and hospitalised in our hospital over the last 10 years.

Materials and Methods: The number of admissions and hospitalisation rates of patients with COPD admitted to our hospital which is one of the Turkey's leading university education and research hospitals specialising in respiratory diseases with a capacity of 405 beds, between 2015 and 2024 were compared by year. Hospital records were accessed from the electronic data system. The level of statistical significance was accepted as $p < 0.05$.

Results: In the last 10 years, a total of 1,691,360 outpatient chest clinics were held, of which 17.9% were coded as J44 and its subcategories with ICD10 classification diagnosed as COPD disease. The number of patients admitted during this period was 987,486, of which 20.2% (199,060 patients) were reported as having COPD. Although the frequency of visits of patients with COPD was found to be 1.52, it was calculated that all patients had 1.26 visits. Patients with COPD presented significantly more often ($p < 0.05$). Over the 10-year period, 18.4% of our patients who attended the outpatient clinic were hospitalised. Of these hospitalised patients, 68.2% (25,016) were male. The mean male age was 61.48 ± 12.54 years and the mean female age was 63.01 ± 13.19 years ($p < 0.01$). Female inpatients were found to be older than female outpatients ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion: Over a 10-year period, it was found that more than 25,000 patients visited the outpatient clinic each year and 30% of them were admitted to hospital. When outpatients and inpatients were compared in terms of male/female ratio and age, it was found that the inpatients were older, and the male/female ratio did not change.

Conclusion: COPD is an increasingly important cause of morbidity, disability and mortality worldwide (Adeloye et al., 2022; Boers et al., 2023). It is important to analyse the demographics of patients requiring

hospital admission. Future studies can be planned to analyse the reasons for hospitalisation and preventive strategies can be reconsidered according to the reasons for hospitalisation.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

COPD, hospitalisation, admission

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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